

“NANOSANDWICH” STRUCTURES UNDER IMPACT LOADINGS

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SUMMARY

This paper deals with the effect of nanoparticles dispersion into laminate composites and its application as face sheets to sandwich composites. The energy absorption and failure mechanisms changes, due to the formation of nanostructures inside the face sheets, are investigated under dynamic loadings.

Keywords: Sandwich Composites, Impact Loadings, Nanoclay, Graphene nanosheets

INTRODUCTION

According to Schubel et al. [1], the use of composite sandwich structures is increasing in the aerospace and marine industry, as well as in other areas where a lightweight material with elevated flexural stiffness is required. The design concept behind these structures is the increase in flexural stiffness by placing two stiff, strong and thin face sheets estranged by a lightweight thicker flexible core. By employing this strategy, the moment of inertia is enhanced and consequently the flexural properties increase while keeping the weight practically unaffected. According to Vinson [2], as face sheets carry most of the load, an optimal design for sandwich composite structures must take into consideration the face sheet response to static and dynamic loads. Unfortunately, as discussed by Lim and his coworkers [3], most of the previous studies have focused on the strength capacity of sandwich structures under quasi-static loading. However, Abrate [4] called attention to the response of sandwich composite structures to impact loadings. According to him, this class of structures is susceptible damage caused by foreign objects impact. The composite sandwich structures response to low velocity impact have been the focus of various researchers.

According to Mines and collaborators [5], the low velocity impact of composite sandwich panels (to this investigation structures and panels have the same meaning) covers the response from sub-critical damage to full perforation. Furthermore, an important point of interest investigated by Mines et al [5] was the relationship between the peak impact force and the damaged area. They concluded that core density has direct influence on damage propagation and energy absorption. Another issue, i.e. the sandwich composite rate-sensitivity, was investigated by Hazizan and Cantwell [6]. They demonstrated that foam based sandwich composites are insensitive to crosshead displacement rate over a large range (0.1 – 1000 mm/min). According to Ávila [7], variations at sandwich composite core density, as in functionally graded sandwich

structures, have direct effect into damage mechanism and the overall sandwich structure behaviour. Laurin and Vizzini [8] went further, as they demonstrated that by placing graphite/epoxy reinforcement through-thickness in a foam core enhances the normal energy absorption of foam-core sandwich structures. Still, they called our attention to the fact that there is no linear relationship between the increase on energy absorption and the addition of stiffness introduced. Suvorov and Dvorak [9] also tried to enhance the sandwich energy absorption by placing an interlayer material between the face sheet and the foam core. Their mathematical model seems to be encouraging. Nevertheless, no experimental data was provided to validate the model.

Ávila et al [10] showed that failure mechanisms of laminated composites (in the present investigation face sheets) can be influenced by nano-structures formed by nanoparticles dispersed into epoxy systems. According to them, the presence of nanoclay into fiber glass/epoxy composites lead to a more intense formation of delaminated areas after a low velocity impact test (LVI). This phenomenon was attributed to interlaminar shear forces caused by the intercalated nano-structures inside the epoxy system. Furthermore, the energy absorption of these laminates increased by 48% with dispersion of 5 wt% of nanoclays. Another important issue described by Li et al [11] is that, when sandwich composites were submitted to LVI tests, there was impact weave propagation inside the two distinct materials, i.e. face sheets and core. Ávila et al [12] demonstrated that nano-modified laminated composites had their natural frequencies altered by nano-structures formed inside the laminated. A crossing mode, 4th mode higher than the 3rd mode, was reported by Ávila et al [12] with the addition of 5 wt% of montmorillonite to fiber glass/epoxy laminates. This paper focus on the effect of nanoclay dispersed into an epoxy/fiber glass composite and its influence on the sandwich composites response to low velocity impact tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Ten sandwich panels were evaluated during the course of this research. The face sheets of the sandwich panel were fiber glass/nano-modified epoxy system laminates. The epoxy system was made of *bisphenol A* resin and an amine hardener, i.e. RemLam M and HY956, from Hunstman Inc. The nanoclay used in this research was organic modified montmorillonite produced by Southern Clay Inc. (Cloisite 30B). The nanoclay content employed was 0 wt% (control), 1 wt%, 2 wt%, 5 wt% and 10 wt%. Eight layers of plain weave woven fabric fiber glass with aerial density of 200 g/m² were employed, resulting in a cured plate with thickness of 0.8 mm and a fiber volume ratio of 0.65. The core used for the sandwich panel was closed-cell PS foam (Styrofoam®). This foam has a density of 35 kg/m³. The core was 25.4 mm thick. During the face sheet preparation, the nanoclay dispersion process into the epoxy system followed the procedure describe in Ávila et al [12]. A dispersant agent, acetone, was employed to improve the mixing process. The degassing stage was required to eliminate bubbles generated during the mechanical mixing, as well as to eliminate the dispersant agent, i.e. acetone. After this procedure, the hand lay-up with vacuum assisted cure was performed. The sandwich panel was fabricated by bonding the cured face sheets to the core material with the same epoxy system applied during the laminate consolidation. A vacuum bagging technique was used to ensure a uniform pressure during the bonding procedure. The final

sandwich panel was a square plate of 300 x 300 mm dimensions with an overall thickness of 27.0 mm and mass of 0.52 kg.

According to Koo [13], during the nanoparticles dispersion into polymeric matrices nano-structures are formed. The two most common detection techniques to nano-structures identification are X-ray diffraction and electronic microscopy. In this research, X-ray diffraction (XRD) experiments were carried out on a Shimadzu XRD-6000 X-ray diffract meter with Cu ($\lambda=0.154$ nm) irradiation at 40 kV and 30 mA using a Ni filter. Data were recorded in the range from 2 to 80 deg in a continuous scanning at 2 degrees per minute and sampling pitch of 0.02 deg. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) used was a LEO model 1430VP. In all cases, a gold thin film was placed on the surface of the sample to able to scan its structure. As this research deals with dynamic loadings, in addition to the traditional nanoparticles dispersion analysis, information about the sandwich response under indentation must be supplied.

According to Hazizan and Cantwell [6], during impact events sandwich structures absorb significant energy in contact deformations around the impact area. Thus, a series of indentation tests were carried out using an INSTRON universal testing machine at crosshead displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min. The indentation tests were conducted using a hemi-spherical indenter of 10 mm diameter. The sandwich panels were loaded up to a force with same magnitude of the ones recorded during the low velocity impact tests. As described by Abrate [4], during the loading phase of the impact, the contact force P is related to the indentation α by $P = C\alpha^n$. The load-indentation data were fitted to this equation to yield the values of n and C for each group of sandwich panels. Once the indentation tests were performed, the following steps are the low velocity impact tests and failure mode analysis. Following the ASTM D 5628-01 standard [12], the dart has a hemispherical nose with a radius of 10.0 ± 0.1 mm. During the impact event, the load-time history is recorded by a data acquisition system with a frequency of 50 kHz rate by an A/D data acquisition board. In contrast with traditional low-velocity impact (LVI) tests performed, the dart is not embraced after the first impact. On the contrary, it is kept free so that it can strike back on the plate as many times as the plate reverses its direction of motion. By applying this strategy, it is possible to evaluate the amount of damage sustained by the sandwich panels. After the LVI tests the damage was measured using image correlation technique. Public domain image correlation software called ImageJ was employed. Finally, an experimental procedure must have its analytical companion model. To achieve this goal, the model proposed by Schubel and collaborators [1] was modified.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Following Schubel et [1], the load pulse can be expressed by a half-sine wave as,

$$f(t) = P_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t\right) \quad (1)$$

By integrating $f(t)$ from 0 to $T/4$, it is possible to obtain the maximum load

$$P_0 = \frac{2\pi m v}{T} \quad (2)$$

Notice that v can be obtained by direct measuring or by applying the energy balance equation. Schubel and his collaborators expressed the incoming velocity in terms of impact energy (E) to obtain the maximum load. They described the maximum load as

$$P_0 = \frac{2\pi}{T} \sqrt{2mE} \quad (3)$$

To be able to compute the panel stiffness (k), let's assume that force-deflection response is linear under low velocity impact. From the previous assumption and the pulse duration estimation described by Schubel et al [1], the panel stiffness can be calculated by the following equation,

$$k = \frac{4\pi^2 m}{T^2} \quad (4)$$

Notice that panel stiffness (k) can also be calculated by the slope of static-deflection curve of the upper face sheet. In this research, T is measured directly from the low velocity impact tests and the mass is known. Notice that by substituting equation (4) into the mass spring model described in Mines et al [5], equation (2) can be obtained.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

By studying Figure 1A, it is possible to conclude that X-ray diffraction (XRD) tests revealed that rather than exfoliated into the epoxy system, the Cloisite 30B nanoclays were in the intercalated form.

Figure 1. (a) XRD signature; (b) TEM micrograph with intercalated nano-structures

Another important issue that must be addressed is the matrix saturation limit regarding the nanoclay content. The basal spacing calculated using Bragg's law indicates an increase from 1.35 nm to 1.38 nm when the nanoclay content changed from 5 wt% to 10 wt%. Yet, the amount of nanoclay is twice as much for the 10 wt% nanoclay content specimens and the XRD intensity increases only 57%. This unexpected reduction on the diffraction intensity is an indication of a disordered swollen structure, as demonstrated by Fan et al [14]. Likewise, Ranade et al [15] stated that it could be an evidence of a

small amount of nanoclay that does not get exfoliated or intercalated, but remains in its own identity leading to an immiscible nano system. This seems the case for the 10 wt% concentration samples. This hypothesis can be visualized in Figure 1B show the intercalated nanostructure can be observed. A partially exfoliated/intercalated system is most likely to occur due to the dispersion system used. In summary, they believed that dispersion process is controlled not only by the nanoparticle morphology but it is also affected by the manufacturing process.

The load-indentation depth curve for the face sheets were obtained based on the methodology described in Zenkert et al [16] and the experimental load-central displacement curve. A nonlinear curve fitting is used to obtain the 1.5 power law equations. The results are shown in Figure 2. The C coefficients obtained are proportional to the square root of indenter tip. Note that for sandwich composites, the n coefficient is lower than 1.5. Hazizan and Cantwell [6] attributed this lower value to the compliance of the test machine. A more reasonable explanation for the phenomenon was provided by Fatt and Park [17]. According to them, the sandwich panel response can be characterized by the superposition of two effects, that is, the bending of the upper face sheet and the core crushing in the areas below and around the indenter. The core crushing effect can be the reason for the n coefficient low value.

Figure 2. Indentation test results

To be able to understand the impact response of sandwich composites with nano-modified face sheets a series of LVI tests were performed. The energies employed were enough to cause damage ranging from a barely visible delamination and perforation. In all cases, the core material is the same; by applying this strategy the core density effect is avoided. Table 1 shows the LVI test parameters. Note that for each energy span, there are two types of impact tests. The first one corresponds to a configuration with the minimum mass (tup + load cell + support) and maximum velocity (C-1), while the second one (C-2) is the opposite, i.e. maximum load and minimum velocity. The objective is to investigate the impact velocity and mass effects on damage formation and the sandwich panel response to these variations.

Table 1. LVI test parameters

Energy	Height [m]		Mass [kg]		Velocity [m/s]	
	C-1	C-2	C-1	C-2	C-1	C-2
25	2.36	0.69	1.079	3.717	6.80	3.56
30	1.91	0.82	1.603	3.717	6.12	4.02
35	2.23	0.96	1.603	3.717	6.62	4.34
40	2.54	1.09	1.603	3.717	7.06	4.64
45	2.15	1.23	2.127	3.717	6.49	4.92
50	2.39	1.37	2.127	3.717	6.86	5.19
55	2.63	1.51	2.127	3.717	7.18	5.44
60	2.30	1.65	2.659	3.717	6.72	5.68
65	2.49	1.78	2.659	3.717	6.99	5.91
70	2.69	1.92	2.659	3.717	7.26	6.14
75	----	2.06	-----	3.717	-----	6.35

Damage observed on sandwich panels caused by the tup impact can be classified in six categories: (i) barely visible damage; (ii) sub-critical damage, i.e. upper face sheet cracking and core indentation; (iii) upper face sheet tearing and core crushing; (iv) lower face sheet and core debonding; (v) lower face sheet cracking; (vi) lower face sheet tearing and perforation. Figure 3A-F shows each one of these categories.

Figure 3. Sandwich panel damage categories

Figure 4A gives the force versus time data for a 5 wt% panel showing the effects of impact velocity. For lower velocities, i.e. up to 4.34 m/s, the impact period seems to be approximately the same. However, for higher velocities (≥ 5.19 m/s) a decrease on impact period was observed. As it can be noticed in equation (5), stiffness is inversely proportional to the impact period. However, taking into consideration the same panel stiffness, remember we are dealing with panels with 5wt% nanoclay, the decrease on impact period must be explained by the failure mechanism. Higher velocities imply

naturally higher energy and a much higher impulse (force/unit of time). A higher impulse will cause a greater localized failure, mainly into core. Core crushing will occur most likely below the tup. This localized core crush contributes to the face sheet failure due to absence of an elastic base. Velocities up to 4.64 m/s produced sub-critical damage, i.e. before upper face sheet tearing. At low velocities and consequently small energy levels, a large part of the impact energy is easily dissipated by the face sheet first and the remaining energy is absorbed by core. When the velocity increases to around 5.19 m/s the upper skin tearing and core crushing is observed. This failure mechanism can be explained by a large impulse which caused a high localized damage, as there was not enough time to impact wave propagation through regions outside below the tup area. This phenomenon is more evident for high energy levels, i.e. >50 J, where the impact wave propagates through the panel thickness right below the tup impact and no significant damage was notice outside the impact projected area. Upper skin tearing and lower skin damage was notice when the velocity reached 5.44 m/s or higher. It is a well known fact that as the energy gets bigger, the damage severity also increases. Perforation with lower skin tearing was experimented for velocities higher than 6.99 m/s. Figure 4B allows us to investigate the mass effect on sandwich panel response to low velocity impact. The velocity was kept higher than 6.3 m/s while the mass changed from 1.08 Kg to 3.7 Kg. The damage caused by these impacts ranged from a barely visible (lower mass) to perforation. As the velocity was kept near constant, the pulse duration could be considered approximately the same. Another important issue is that face sheet damage mechanism changes with the amount of nanoparticle dispersed.

Figure 4. Force versus time for a 5 wt% panel. (a) Impact velocity effect. (b) Impact mass effect.

Figure 5A-C provides the force versus time data for condition 2 (C-2) where the energies were 25, 50 and 75 joules, respectively. A change on impact pulse is noticed for the 25 joule energy level. According to equation (4), impact pulse is inversely proportional to panel stiffness. Thus, as the panel with 5 wt% nanoclay content has the smallest period (26.89 ms), it must have the largest stiffness. Another issue is that pulse period decreases with the addition of nanoclay up to 5 wt%. The 10 wt% panel has a pulse period 14.96% higher than the 5 wt% panel. The same pattern was noticed for the mid and high range energy, i.e. 50J and 75 J, respectively. As described by equation (4), higher impact period implies into smaller panel stiffness. Therefore, it is possible to

conclude that the “extra amount” of nanoparticle did not increase the panel stiffness, in the contrary; it causes a decrease on stiffness. Once the saturation limit is reached, the additional nanoclay dispersed into the matrix precipitates into the form of immiscible nanostructures, which can be sources of cracks nucleation, as they are stress concentration “hot spots”. This hypothesis can be corroborated by the XRD tests, where a significant increase on diffracted energy was notice. Notice that a high diffracted energy is also a sign of large entropy. This increase on entropy can be caused by these precipitated third phase.

Figure 5. Force versus time data. (a) Low range energy; (b) mid range energy; (c) high range energy

The model predictions (figure 6) were compared against the experimental data with good agreement. However, for large energies (> 50 J), a small deviation was observed. This can be due to the intense core crushing under the impact area. Notice that for the largest energy 75J, a 6% difference between the predicted value and the experimental data is notice. The core crushing rate effect must be included in the present model.

Figure 6. Model prediction versus experimental data

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of nanoclay addition to fiber glass/epoxy systems and its use on face sheet for sandwich composites was investigated. X-ray diffraction tests and electronic microscopy observation proven the existence of intercalated nano-structures dispersed into the epoxy system. The sudden drop on X-ray diffraction intensity seems to be an evidence of entropy increase as result of an immiscible phase precipitation. It seems that epoxy system has a “saturation” limit between 5 wt% and 10 wt% of nanoclay content. A model to predict the peak reaction for during the low velocity impact was proposed based on pulse duration. The model predictions are limited as the core yielding was not taken into consideration. The addition of nanoclay gives the impression of having effect on pulse duration, as they increase the face sheet laminate stiffness and consequently the panel overall bending rigidity. The pulse period appears to be independent of velocity. Nonetheless, mass changes can affect the pulse period. The nanoclay dispersion on epoxy system could be the reason for an increase on face sheet stiffness and the panel overall rigidity when low velocity impact tests were performed. The nanoclay increase on stiffness looks like to be overshadow by the core crushing during the failure mode transition stages.

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